

CONGRUENCES WITH FACTORIALS MODULO P

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Abstract

It is proved that the number of $a \in \{1, \dots, p-1\}$ which can be represented as a product of two factorials is at least $\frac{3}{4}p + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2)$. This improves the result given by Garaev et.al. [Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., 356 (2004)5089-5102]. Beyond this, we pose several conjectures.

1. Introduction

Throughout this paper, p is an odd prime. In [6,F11], it is conjectured that about p/e of the residue classes $a \pmod{p}$ are missed by the sequence $n!$. If this were so, the sequence $n!$ modulo p should assume about $(1 - 1/e)p$ distinct values. Some results of this spirit have appeared in [1]. The above conjecture immediately implies that if p is large enough, then every residue class a modulo p can be represented as a product of two factorials. Unfortunately, this conjecture appears to be very hard. Various additive and multiplicative congruences with factorials have been considered in [2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8].

We denote by $F_l(a, p-1)$ the number of solutions to the congruence

$$\prod_{i=1}^l n_i! \equiv a \pmod{p}, \quad 1 \leq n_1, \dots, n_l \leq p-1,$$

where $a \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$. Let $V_l(p-1)$ be the number of $a \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ for which $F_l(a, p-1) > 0$, that is,

$$V_l(p-1) = \# \left\{ \prod_{i=1}^l n_i! \pmod{p} \mid 1 \leq n_1, \dots, n_l \leq p-1 \right\}.$$

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Garaev et.al. [3] proved that

$$V_2(p - 1) \geq \frac{5}{8}p + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2).$$

In this paper we prove the following result.

Theorem.

$$V_2(p - 1) \geq \frac{3}{4}p + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2).$$

We pose the following conjectures.

Conjecture 1. *For any odd prime p , any integer $a \in \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}$ can be represented as a product of two factorials except for $p = 11$ and $a = 7$.*

Conjecture 2. *If a is a factorial, $a \neq 0$, then there are infinitely many primes p for which there are no integers n with $a \equiv n! \pmod{p}$.*

Conjecture 3. *Let a be an integer. If for any prime p there is an integer n with $a \equiv n! \pmod{p}$, then $a = -1$, $a = 0$, or a is a factorial.*

2. Proof of the Theorem

Lemma(Zhang [9, 10]). Let $N(p)$ denote the number of all pairs (a, b) with $a, b \in \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}$ for which a and b are of opposite parity and $ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Then

$$N(p) = \frac{1}{2}p + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2).$$

Proof of Theorem. Define

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \{ (a, b) \mid ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}, 2 \mid a, 2 \nmid b, a, b = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1 \}, \\ I_2 &= \{ (a, b) \mid ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}, 2 \nmid a, 2 \mid b, a, b = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1 \}, \\ I_3 &= \{ (a, b) \mid ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}, 2 \mid a, 2 \mid b, a, b = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1 \}, \\ I_4 &= \{ (a, b) \mid ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}, 2 \nmid a, 2 \nmid b, a, b = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1 \}. \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that

$$|I_2| + |I_4| = |I_1| + |I_4| = \frac{p - 1}{2}, \tag{1}$$

$$|I_1| + |I_3| = |I_1| + |I_4| = \frac{p - 1}{2}. \tag{2}$$

Hence $|I_1| = |I_2|$, $|I_3| = |I_4|$. Thus, by the lemma we have

$$|I_1| = |I_2| = \frac{1}{2}N(p) = \frac{1}{4}p + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2). \tag{3}$$

By (1), (2), and (3) we obtain

$$|I_3| = |I_4| = \frac{1}{4}p + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2). \tag{4}$$

Let $a, b \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ with $ab \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Wilson's Theorem implies that (the similar arguments appear in [1, 2, 3])

$$-1 \equiv (p-1)! \equiv (-1)^{a-1}(a-1)!(p-a)! \pmod{p}$$

and

$$-1 \equiv (p-1)! \equiv (-1)^{b-1}b!(p-b-1)! \pmod{p}.$$

Hence,

$$a \equiv (-1)^a a!(p-a)! \pmod{p}, \text{ and}$$

$$a \equiv (-1)^{b+1} a \cdot b!(p-b-1)! \equiv (-1)^{b+1}(b-1)!(p-b-1)! \pmod{p}.$$

Thus, if a is even or if b is odd, then a can be represented as a product of two factorials. This implies that if $(a, b) \in I_1 \cup I_3 \cup I_4$, then $a \in V_2(p-1)$.

Therefore, by (3) and (4) we have

$$V_2(p-1) \geq |I_1| + |I_3| + |I_4| \geq \frac{3p}{4} + O(p^{1/2}(\log p)^2).$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

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